

USING ENGLISH IN THE CLASSROOM

Ergasheva Umida

The teacher of practical English language and literature department, FSU.

Niyozmatova Oygul

Fergana state University English language and literature faculty, third year student.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990460>

Abstract: Taking a general English language course can offer numerous benefits. It can help you improve your communication skills, increase your confidence, become more culturally aware, expand your career opportunities, improve your academic performance, and achieve personal growth. English language helps to you speak more fluently when you go to foreign countries and also communicate with strangers without difficulties and misunderstandings. Utilizing English in the classroom is also beneficial for all pupils and students because their speech grows by speaking each other. Besides pupils' speech is corrected by teachers during lesson if they use English whole lesson. The primary purpose of language is to communicate effectively, and spoken English empowers students to express themselves with clarity and confidence. A strong command of spoken English enables students to articulate their thoughts, ideas, and emotions precisely, both in the classroom and beyond.

Key words: speech, purpose, learner, function, achievement, opportunity, confidence, culturally aware, career, communication skills, broaden our mind, pronunciation, intonation, dialogue, classroom activities, practice, pause and instructions.

Speaking only in English helps students begin speaking English internally. The only way to become fluent in a language is by being immersed in the language. An English only policy in class requires them to negotiate the learning process in English. Students speaking another language distract other English learners.

English language plays an essential role in our lives as it helps in communication. It is the main language for studying any subject all over the world. English is important for students as it broadens their minds, develops emotional skills, improve the quality of life by providing job opportunities. There are two important factors that can lead to your students becoming more confident in listening to and speaking English:

regular exposure to spoken English and hearing the language as it is used for communication
regular practise in speaking English so that they develop confidence in using the language, becoming familiar with its rhythms and comfortable with pronouncing it.

It is important for your students to have many opportunities to engage in real and meaningful communications in English. One good way of learning a language is by immersion, where it is used in daily life. This is how your students learned their home languages. Since English plays an important role in India, many of them may be learning English this way as well. But even if your students do not have much exposure to English outside of the classroom, they can still make significant progress in learning the language if they get lots of practice listening to and speaking it inside the classroom.

This unit explores how you can increase the number of interactions in English in your classroom. This way, speaking English will not be something that students are scared of or worried about; instead, it will become an easy and natural way for you to communicate with your students, and for them to communicate with each other. The unit also shows you some

ways to help your students practise speaking so that they become more familiar with the rhythm and pronunciation of the language, so that it becomes more natural to them.

Everyday classroom activities can provide meaningful authentic opportunities for your students to regularly listen to and speak English. Such small activities can include things like greeting your students, taking attendance, introducing a new topic or giving instructions. Using English like this in the classroom is beneficial for your students because they get to hear more English and they hear how the language is used in real-life communication. It also gives them a purpose for speaking English. In order to be able to communicate using English, students need to be able to hear and speak the language regularly in lots of different settings and with lots of different tasks, not just in textbook exercises.

Discuss these questions with a colleague if you can.

greeting students

taking attendance

giving instructions

checking previous knowledge

managing behaviour

encouraging students to speak

praising your students

giving homework

saying goodbye

talking to your students about their lives .

There are some English phrases that you can use for each situation. Write some more phrases in each box.

Mr Jhadav uses more English in his English class

Mr Jhadav has been teaching English to secondary students for a number of years but his students are not confident enough to speak it themselves. He decides to speak more English in the classroom to help them learn the language. Although he finds it difficult at first, he notices that his students soon get used to hearing more English in class.

I was thinking about my last class and how much English I use. I tend to mostly just read out the lesson. I'd like to use more spoken English in the classroom. I used to use quite a lot of English when I was studying to become a teacher, but now I am out of practice. So before starting to use more English with my students, I decided to practise on my own. I tried to think of the things that I usually say to students in students' home language, like 'Today we are doing Lesson 3', and 'Can you read the next line please?' I practised these phrases over and over to myself in English and out loud, so that they would sound natural when I used them with the students. They looked at me with some surprise. At first, no one responded. So I repeated the instruction to open their books two more times. Eventually, they all had their books open on the correct page. Then I got my own book and I showed them the picture on page 3. I repeated the question: It was quiet, but I waited a few moments for my students to reply. Eventually one student said 'tired'. So I replied: 'Good! Yes, I think he's tired.'

From this day, I started using more and more English with my students in class. I began to give classroom instructions like 'Can you read the next line please?' I was surprised at how quickly they got used to my speaking to them in English. Sometimes I had to repeat the instructions a number of times, but soon most of them understood.

I am slowly starting to use more and more English in the classroom, and I am getting more confident about it. I am sure I make some mistakes and my pronunciation isn't perfect, but my students don't seem to notice. Sometimes I have problems with vocabulary, and I can't think of a word or phrase I want to use in English. When that happens, I try to think of another way to say what I want in English. As a last resort, I use the Hindi word. I try to make a note of the words I don't know. After class, I ask a colleague or look the word up in the dictionary. This is helping me to improve my English too! And I notice that my students are beginning to become more confident with speaking a few words of English when they reply to me. I try not to correct them immediately but listen to the sense of what they are saying.

To summarize, Speaking and using English in the classroom is extremely major activity for all students and pupils because by learning this language in classroom they can hang out with all people in the world. So that, "never stop learning because life never stop teaching".

References:

1. <https://www.open.edu>
2. <https://www.english-room.com>
3. <https://ejournal.mandalanursa>
4. <https://theindianpublicschool.ora>
5. <https://www.thoughtco.com>

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY